

THE PROBLEM OF INSOMNIA - CAUSES OF SLEEP DISORDER, REMEDIES AT HOME

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Abstract. *What to do to fight insomnia at home? Insomnia and other types of sleep disorders are almost a worldwide problem. When someone "suffers from insomnia", we mean not only short sleep duration, but also difficulty falling asleep and frequent awakenings, which prevents rest and wakes up in the morning with a feeling of fatigue. Insomnia at night is familiar to almost everyone, daytime sleeplessness of children is also considered as a special problem, it can be a characteristic of the child or a symptom of a nervous system disorder. If insomnia bothers a person from time to time, then there is no need to treat it with drugs. Let's take a look at the causes of insomnia, what to do if you can't sleep at night, and expert advice on how to overcome insomnia at home.*

Keywords: *Is it possible to fight insomnia without the help of specialists, How can I help myself to fall asleep without drugs, What can be done additionally to improve sleep?*

THE EFFECT OF SLEEP DISORDERS ON THE ORGANISM

There are people for whom 5-6 hours of sleep is enough to restore their strength, and for others, 8-9 hours of sleep, which is the norm for adults, is not enough. These are related to the individual characteristics of a person, as well as the circadian rhythm, which allows us to divide people into "birds", "owls" and "pigeons" depending on the convenient time for sleeping and waking up.

As a rule, a healthy person easily falls asleep within 7-10 minutes, sleeps through the night without waking up, and wakes up in the morning refreshed and ready for a new day. Every day, the situation of a person suffering from insomnia is completely different. In such cases, how can you improve your sleep, what should you do to improve it, when should you go to the doctor and in what situations can you deal with the problem of insomnia on your own? What should people who do not sleep well do at home and what should be changed?

Sleep disturbance, lack of a full period to restore mental and physical strength is one of the factors that not only significantly worsens the general condition, but also causes disruption of almost all body systems. Sleep deprivation was one of the torture methods used in ancient China. Insomnia can cause severe headaches, confusion, fainting, and hallucinations. Modern studies on the effects of lack of sleep on the body have shown that even with a slight lack of sleep, brain activity is impaired, which affects the ability to perceive, think, and make logical judgments.

Prolonged lack of sleep leads to such consequences. But the usual lack of sleep at night can slow down work performance, harm health, and lead to a state similar to depression. In fact, the only question that arises when suffering from insomnia is how to fall asleep? However, first of all, it is necessary to understand the factors that cause sleep disorders.

WHAT CAUSES INSOMNIA?

The causes of insomnia are very diverse, ranging from poor nutrition to hormonal disorders. The most common factors affecting the depth and duration of sleep include:

Conditions for uncomfortable or unusual sleep: noisy or bright rooms, hot, cold, lack of oxygen in the room, smoke mixtures, especially tobacco smoke, strong smells, uncomfortable bed, pillow, etc.

Before going to bed or during the day, taking food, drink or drugs that stimulate nerve activity (coffee, green tea, chocolate, cola, and "refreshing" drinks based on caffeine and guarana). Nicotine contained in tobacco smoke has a negative effect on sleep even in passive smoking;

Changes in lifestyle, including short-term: travel, business trip, hospitality, change of job, place of residence, marital status;

Stressful situations, especially in rigid, strong emotional individuals who do not "let go" of unpleasant events and thoughts. The problem of people suffering from chronic insomnia is separated. Often they are frightened by the approach of the night, they think: "I have insomnia, how can I sleep?" a circle of questions is formed, which in turn causes stress and anxiety, the first stages of the sleep phase do not begin in naja;

Diseases, because they are associated not only with insomnia as a symptom of the disease, but also pain, tingling, convulsions, frequent urination, cough, breathing difficulties, internal and external triggers does not allow to sleep due to overreaction.

Physiological hormonal changes in the body can also cause short-term insomnia. Women often have problems with sleep before and during menstruation, they often complain that insomnia does not go away for 3 days. Hormonal imbalance due to these physiological processes lasts about 3-4 days. He finds a solution on his own without requiring treatment;

Some medications affect sleep. Caffeine contained in Citramon stimulates the nervous system. Drugs containing broncholithin and pseudoephedrine used in ventilation can cause insomnia;

Violation of the circadian and daily rhythm: switching to other time zones, alternation of day and evening work shifts, active rest and entertainment in the evening, as well as the habit of sleeping long on weekends;

Depressive states of varying severity.

EFFECTS OF BEVERAGES AND FOOD PRODUCTS

Seemingly "innocuous" foods rich in simple carbohydrates (candy and sweets, sodas, etc.) eaten before bed can cause a short-term drop in blood glucose levels, resulting in The feeling of hunger prevents sleep.

Experts do not recommend including simple carbohydrates in the evening menu, they recommend eating wheat bread with a piece of cheese, banana, milk, eggs 1-1.5 hours before going to bed. It is known that fatty, hard-to-digest food prevents the onset of sleep. However, somnologists-scientists say that the widespread opinion that you should sleep on an empty stomach, as well as the advice of dieters that you should eat 3 hours before going to bed, have a negative effect on the process of falling asleep and sleep. In turn, the lack of sleep leads to an increase in the need for energy in the body, which causes a feeling of hunger and a violation of the diet.

It should be noted that alcohol also affects sleep. The idea that a small amount of wine or brandy helps to fall asleep has not been fully confirmed by researchers. Indeed, alcohol has a sedative effect, but this effect is very short-lived. Even if he falls asleep after drinking a glass, a person wakes up in the phase of deep sleep: alcohol has a negative effect on this phase. This method of combating insomnia does not help to get a long rest.

IS IT POSSIBLE TO FIGHT INSOMNIA WITHOUT THE HELP OF EXPERTS?

It is possible to deal with some of the factors that cause insomnia independently, this can be achieved by changing the daily routine and conditions for sleeping, reducing the sensitivity to stimuli or replacing the drugs taken with their analogues. If your sleep is affected by depression or traditional methods to improve sleep are ineffective, you should consult a specialist for drug treatment.

There are a number of other factors that cause insomnia, which cannot be eliminated independently. In such cases, specialist help is required. They are:

Consequences of concussion, neuroinfection, neurological and psychotic conditions and other diseases of the nervous system;

Diseases that prevent sleep or wake up due to pain or significant discomfort;

Sleep apnea, breathing disorders during sleep;

Insomnia of genetic etiology, hereditary factors.

The treatment of such disorders begins with the therapy of the main disease, the treatment is carried out along with anti-sleep drugs. Today, more than 30 diseases that increase the risk of insomnia have been identified. In 20 percent of cases, doctors cannot identify the causative factors.

Regardless of the cause of the condition, it begins to affect your health almost immediately, especially if the insomnia lasts for 3 days or more. If the sleep disorder lasts longer than a week, urgent measures should be taken. How can you help yourself, what to do against insomnia at home and how do sleep specialists - somnologists-doctors solve this problem?

The general principles of treating insomnia are based on the factors that cause it to occur. Since 80% of sleep disorders are secondary, this approach helps in many cases. In order to eliminate the causes and make the treatment really effective, it may be necessary to consult with a psychotherapist, psychiatrist, medical treatment profile doctors (gastroenterologist, cardiologist, etc.).

Often, sleep disorders are observed in those who are often on duty and on business trips, as well as those who simply go to bed late and wake up late. If insomnia has developed due to these factors, what should be done at home to solve the problem? Recommendations for normalizing the agenda will help in this. A doctor can prescribe melatonin, a synthetic analog of the sleep hormone, to quickly reset when time zones or work schedules change.

HOW CAN I HELP MYSELF TO SLEEP WITHOUT DRUGS?

Folk medicine recipes can be used as an auxiliary tool in the diagnosis of insomnia. It is better to start the struggle by revising the daily routine and diet.

According to scientists' research, the characteristics of sleep depend on the level of serotonin and melatonin hormones. Experts have identified amino acids that affect the production of serotonin and are available in food. By making changes to your diet, you can get rid of insomnia without medication.

For example, tryptophan amino acid is found in the following products: turkey meat, pumpkin seeds, seafood, milk, nuts, eggs.

Cherries and walnuts are recommended to stimulate the production of natural melatonin, which aids sleep.

Scientists recommend increasing magnesium-containing products in the diet. More than 70 percent of the population suffers from magnesium deficiency, which leads to high levels of

restlessness and difficulty falling asleep. Optimal suppliers of magnesium are fruits and vegetables, bananas, cabbage, almonds.

Thus, by changing the menu, you can improve your health and also eliminate serious problems such as insomnia.

WHAT CAN BE DONE AS AN ADDITIONAL APPROACH TO IMPROVE SLEEP?

Taking a hot bath 1-1.5 hours before going to bed, reading or doing sedentary activities, meditation, and relaxation practices make it easier to fall asleep. Also check the availability of all the necessary conditions for sleeping in the bedroom: fresh air, darkness (light reduces the production of melatonin), silence.

What to do if insomnia persists? In addition, it is possible to take plant tinctures with a sedative effect or take baths with aromatic oils. If permanent improvement of sleep is not achieved, it is time to consult a specialist.

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